

PREPREG IMPREGNATION: CHARACTERISATION OF PROCESSING VARIABLES

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SUMMARY: The application of low fibre aerial weight (FAW) and low resin content (RC) on continuous solution processed prepreg has become necessary in the composites industry to fit the requirement of making lighter, stiffer and stronger products. The variables involved in the manufacture of low-RC prepreg in the continuous solution process are identified and discussed respectively. Useful calculations based on a fundamental fluid dynamics equation show good agreement with the set values in the current manufacturing process. The limitation of fibre spread and resin impregnation is dependent on; fibre elongation, the radius of the nip rollers, the resin's viscosity and the pressure applied from the nip rollers.

KEYWORDS: Continuous solution processed prepreg, fluid dynamics, fibre elongation, nip roller, resin viscosity, pressure.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous solution processed prepreg manufacturing as illustrated in Figure 1 has recently been popularised due to the flexibility of handling of the high viscous resin system together with the lower investment in facilities compared to the hot-melt process. In the continuous solution process the prepreg has good integral fibre and resin distribution as well as low solvent content. These are the most important benefits for its application compared to the drum winding method which has low facility cost but has about 1-2 percent of volatile content. Though the investment in the facilities for the continuous solution process is much more than the drum winding method, the advantages such as precise quality control and ensured performance, low manufacturing and labour costs owing to a continuous prepreg manufacturing process, the decrease of waste material (because of the more flexible tailored arrangement of the prepreg compared to the short length of drum winding ones), makes the investment worthwhile.

Fig.1 Continuous solution process

Continuous solution impregnating techniques embrace the fields of micromechanics of composite materials and fundamental fluid dynamic. Ahn et al [1-2] and Hayes et al [3-4] have discussed hot-melt impregnating theories in hot-melt processes. Actually, in the fluid dynamics, the equation composed of related variables such as the viscosity of the resin, the impregnating pressure and the line speed in the process is derived from the law of Hagen – Poiseuille with some simplified assumptions. It is more suitable for practical applications.

IMPREGNATION THEORY

Fibre Spread

For the continuous solution process, there is no external fibre spread mechanism such as tension bars which spread fibre strands before going into the first set of nip rollers. The main spreading region is at the small areas during hot nipping. For the nip rollers, the diagram of strand spread before and after nipping is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Width of strand before and after first set of nip rollers.

Fibres are spread at the initial pressure point. The width at the nip point and the width after nipping is affected by the radius of the nip rollers. Fibres cannot be spread indefinitely. The expansion is limited so that fibre breakage will not happen. The nip point, Figure 2,

determines the width of strand after nipping.

Mikito Maki et al [5] addressed the consideration of what caused fibre-breakage. If the fibres are treated as fixed at the initial pressure point and then are spread wider by the nipping pressure to a width of W_2 at the nip point, the length L_2 , is constrained by the fibre strain, ε . Thus, the relationship between the distance of fibre spread zone, L_1 , the oblique length, L_2 and the fibre elongation, ε , can be represented by Equation 1.

$$\frac{L_2 - L_1}{L_1} = \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

If the value on the left side of the equation is larger than the fibre ultimate strain, fibre-breakage will occur. The difference of the width before and after being nipped can be seen from Figure 2 to be

$$L_2 = \sqrt{h^2 + L_1^2} \quad (2)$$

After rearrangement,

$$W_2 \leq W_1 + 2L_1\sqrt{\varepsilon^2 + 2\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

Where W_1 = width of strand before being nipped.

Thus, the factors influencing the width of strand after nipping are clearly revealed. Fibre strain is the critical factor affecting the spreading process. The lower percentage of the fibre strain, the more difficult it is to spread the fibre strands and the more possible it is to break the fibres at nipping. This is why it is harder to make lower fibre aerial weight prepreg by the use of high modulus fibres.

Resin Impregnation

The step of resin impregnation in the hot-melt prepreg manufacturing process is undertaken by heating the pre-coated resin films and pressing the melt resin on to the spread fibre system by hot nip rollers. For the solution process shown in Figure 1, fibre strands have been impregnated as they pass through the resin bath with a predetermined concentration. Therefore, a fixed

amount of resin solution is absorbed by the fibres under a fixed line speed. Fibre strands are then moved into an oven with 110°C hot air to drive off the solvent (methyl ethyl ketone). The fibre strands are then simply spread by the hot nip rollers. The temperature of the oil flowing into the nip rollers is determined from relevant thermal analysis of the applied resin system, which includes the determination of viscosity and gel time at this operating temperature. Generally, the factors involved in the resin impregnation can be specified as follows

- The thickness of prepreg, t : dependent on the fibre aerial weight (FAW) and percentage of resin content (RC%).
- Fibre volume content, V_f : influenced by the resin content of prepreg, density of resin matrix and fibre.
- Resin viscosity, μ : varies with different resin systems and processing temperature.
- Fibre diameter, d : varies with different brands of fibre and/or modulus.
- Pressure applied from nip rollers, P : affecting the results of impregnation.
- Line speed, v : compromised between yield and product quality.

Fig.3 Resin flow into the fibre bed

It is a quite common consideration in micromechanics to assume that all fibres in a unidirectional lamina are aligned parallel to each other and are arranged in a hexagonal or square lattice as shown in Figure 3. In order to simplify the assumptions, the square packing of unidirectional fibres is selected in this paper and is treated as if a fluid flows through two vertical panels when resin is heated and pressed into the fibres. The procedure is to derive an expression for the momentum flux and determine the differential equation for the fluid velocity

[6]. After integration, it becomes an expression with velocity u , pressure drop ΔP , shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$, shear stress τ and the force on flow boundaries. From the law of conservation of momentum, a simple force balance can be used and expressed as

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \quad (4)$$

In order to simplify the calculation it is acceptable to arbitrarily assume that the heated resin flow is a Newtonian fluid. The relationship between shear stress and shear rate is

$$\tau_{xz} = \mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \quad (5)$$

Combining (4) and (5) leads to

$$\mu \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \quad (6)$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu \int d\left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}\right) = \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial z}\right) \int dx \quad (7)$$

$$\Rightarrow \mu \int_0^u du = \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial z}\right) \int_0^r x dx \quad (8)$$

from which the value of u is obtained as

$$u = \frac{1}{2\mu} \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial z}\right) r^2 = \frac{P \cdot r^2}{2 \cdot \mu \cdot l} \quad (9)$$

where

P : Pressure needed for resin impregnation, kg/m^2

μ : Viscosity of resin at impregnating temperature, $kg/m \cdot s$

l : Distance of the path of resin flow, m

u : Resin flow rate, m/s

$2r$: Space between fibres, m

$$\therefore P = \frac{8 \cdot u \cdot \mu \cdot l}{\left(\left[\sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3} \cdot V_f}} - 1 \right] \cdot d \right)^2} \quad (10)$$

The force that the nip rollers need to apply at the impregnating pressure, P, can be calculated from Equation (11).

$$F = P \cdot L \cdot W \quad (11)$$

Where, W is the theoretical width of the prepreg after nipping. The applied pressure read from the gauge can then be calculated from the impregnating force divided by the area of the air cylinder on both sides of the nip roller. The final width of collimated fibre strands must be larger than the initial width as described in [2]. There are two forces competing in determining the fibre spread during the nipping process. One is the fibre tension along the fibre direction and the other is the force acting in the transverse direction which is attributed to the hydrostatic force imposed by the roller in the thickness direction. For an evenly spreading process, the transverse force is much larger than the force acting in the line direction if the fibre tension is appropriately adjusted. Thus, for a given force (F'), the maximum impregnating thickness which is related to the maximum distance of resin flow (l) can be expressed as a function of roller contact length (L), as shown in Figure 3, line speed (v) and viscosity (μ).

$$t' = \left[\frac{8 \cdot g \cdot \left(\frac{F'}{L} \right) \cdot r^4 \cdot \sqrt{R}}{v \cdot \mu \cdot (1 - V_f)^{3/2} \cdot (d + 2r)} \right]^{-1.5} \quad (12)$$

where t' is the maximum impregnating thickness. The theoretical prepreg thickness, t , can be estimated by the fibre density, resin density, FAW (fibre aerial weight, g/m^2) and resin content and it can be expressed as

$$t = \left(\frac{FAW}{\rho_f} + \frac{RW}{\rho_m} \right) \times 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{w} \right) \quad (13)$$

where RW is the weight of matrix per meter squared (g/m^2), ρ_f and ρ_m are the density of fibre and resin respectively. w represents the practical width (m) of prepreg and the value of the ratio is the comparison of practical width and unit width. From the assumption of Seferis et

al, the total volume of collimated fibres before and after nipping may be assumed to remain constant. Therefore, the assumption that the change of thickness, $\Delta t = t' - t$, directly influences the spread width is acceptable. Δt creates another spread zone similar to L_1 in Equation (1) and is proportional to the roller contact angle, θ , which is the included angle between L_1 and L_2 . The new distance of spread zone, L_1' , then is

$$L_1' = \frac{R}{2} \cdot F(\theta) \quad (14)$$

where $F(\theta)$ is a function of the radius of the first set of nip rollers, R , and Δt . So the final width of prepreg, referring to equation (3), can be described as

$$W = W_2 + 2L_1' \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 + 2\varepsilon} \quad (15)$$

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Epoxy-based resin systems (EPO-REG and EPO-LR from Epotech Composite Corp) were impregnated into 12K HTA carbon fibre tows from the Toho Company. The diameter of a single fibre filament is about $7.5 \mu m$ with 1.7% maximum strain. The viscosity of the individual resin system was measured as a function of temperature using a rheometer (TA Instrument) and the data are shown in Figure 4. The whole prepreg manufacturing process was performed using commercial continuous solution prepregger which produces one-meter-width prepreg with 120 meter length per roll. Impregnating theory was demonstrated by three kinds of FAW, 75, 100 and 150 with the same percentage of resin content (25%) in the prepregging process.

Fig.4 Viscosity profiles of epoxy-based resin systems examined in this study.

For $FAW \geq 100 \text{ g/m}^2$, EPO-REG resin system was used to make the prepreg. By contrast, for the lower fibre aerial weight prepreg such as $FAW = 75 \text{ g/m}^2$, due to the corresponding lower resin content, EPO-LR resin system was applied because of its lower viscosity, which may make it easier to spread the fibres. The relevant adjustable processing variables should be classified. This classification is based on the handiness and practicality of these variables on the process. Normally, line speed and nipping pressure are the variables often adjusted. Temperature, which affects the variation of viscosity and the pot life of the matrix is not recommended for change once determined. i.e. viscosity, would be adapted to impregnate and spread the fibre strands. Table 1 shows the basic variables that were applied in this study and the machine is the commercial continuous solution prepregger of Epotech Composite Corporation.

Table 1: Basic processing variables applied on this study

FAW	150	100	75
OD of nip roller (m)	0.315	0.315	0.315
ID of cylinder (m)	0.2	0.2	0.2
Resin type	EPO-REG	EPO-REG	EPO-LR
Temperature of nip rollers ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	90	90	110
Viscosity of matrix at nipping temperature ($\text{kg/m}\cdot\text{s}$)	32	32	4
Line speed (m/s)	0.133	0.133	0.05

The study reported in this paper demonstrates the value of the derived equations applied to the low resin content or lower FAW prepreg manufacturing process. The nipping pressure is the variable adjusted in practice. The relationship between nipping pressure and resin content under the same FAW is then discussed. The temperature of the nip rollers for making different specification prepreg will only be stated in this study. The determined temperature is related to the prepregging viscosity which will influence the flow of the molten resin as well as the possibility of resin overflow in the process. Fibre volume fraction (V_f) can be calculated from the desired RC% and then the space between fibres can be calculated as well. Then the only variable in equation (12) is the force applied on the cylinder of nip rollers to make good quality prepreg, which means efficient impregnation of resin through the thickness of the fibre bed and sufficient fibre spread to give the desired width of prepreg without gaps. After determining the fibre spread zone L_1' as described in Equation (14), the overall prepregging width of prepreg under the applied force can be evaluated and checked to see if the width achieves at least the desired 1 meter width. Actually, the variables from Equation (12) to Equation (14) can all be discussed under different circumstances. However, only a few of them are discussed here for

brevity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 5 and 6 show the applied nipping pressure varying with different FAW and RC% of prepreg during prepregging process. It is clear that the resin impregnation pressure or force needs to be larger to impregnate higher FAW prepreg such as $FAW = 150g/m^2$ in Figure 4 in order to provide a sufficient impregnation through the thickness of the fibre bed, according to the estimation based on Equation (10). However, for FAW150 the practical nipping pressure is overestimated compared to the lower fibre-aerial-weight prepreg, and the variation becomes more apparent as the resin content is reduced. This is owing to the fibre strands being more collimated for higher FAW prepreg than the lower FAW prepreg.

Fig. 5 Applied nipping pressure of first set of nip rollers varying with different FAW and RC%.

For FAW150, there are about 187 strands to be spread but only 125 strands for FAW 100. The higher FAW prepregging process spreads the fibre strands relatively easily to be without any gap. Thus, the nipping pressure in practice might be underestimated for the processing engineer in the workshop because there is no visible gap being observed in the process. However, it is common to find poor impregnated prepreg for the specifications of lower resin content. In this case the middle of the prepreg is poorly wetted. This is because insufficient impregnation pressure is applied by the technicians who make the decision based on the observation of having no gaps during the process. By contrast, the agreement between estimated and practical nipping pressure for lower FAW prepreg such as is demonstrated in Figures 5 and 6 is good. This is due to the larger gaps which exist between each collimated fibre strand before going into the first set of nip rollers. To mend the larger gaps, the additional force for the impregnation needs to be applied on the rollers so that the additional spread zone in Equation (14) can be created. There is no shortage of nipping pressure compared to the higher FAW process;

otherwise, the gaps could not be mended. The calculation steps from Equation (12) to Equation (15) provide a close estimation.

Fig. 6 Applied nipping pressure of first set of nip rollers for $FAW = 75 \text{ g/m}^2$

With regard to the FAW 75 prepreg, only 94 strands are to be spread and it is difficult to spread the fibres without gaps. In addition, the influence of viscosity and line speed on the prepregging results will become critical. It is shown in Figure 4 that the lower viscosity resin system (EPO-LR) will be the better choice to apply on this specification based on the calculation from Equation (10) and Equation (12). If EPO-REG were selected, the nipping pressure would be much higher as demonstrated in Figure 6 and would be increased dramatically with lower resin content.

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